

Synthesis and Characterisation of A Novel Complex Containing Iron(III) and Molybdenum(V)

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Manuscript received 5 February 1981, revised 6 July 1981, accepted 30 October 1981

Anhydrous molybdenum pentachloride reacts with the binuclear iron-salen complex, $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$, to form a compound having the molecular formulae $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}(\text{MoOCl}_5)_2$, in which the MoOCl_5 units are symmetrically coordinated to the oxygen atoms from salen. The spectral, magnetic and polarographic measurements on this complex support its formulation as a complex with four metal ion centres with suitable metal ion requirements. With stability and solubility in aprotic solvents it promises a model for 'nitrogenase' system.

A recent trend in the chemistry of coordination compounds has been the search for complexes containing multi-metal centres and their screening as models of bio-inorganic molecules^{1,2}. While such models are very few to find and are mostly organometallic in nature, some examples are known of stable and soluble complexes with similar or dissimilar metal centres³⁻⁶. In continuation of our earlier study⁷ we report another novel compound containing four metal centres, two iron(III) and two molybdenum(V), representing a model system of 'nitrogenase' type and satisfying the metal ion requirement of the particular enzyme⁸. In this communication we present the preparation and physico-chemical study on this complex with interesting structural features and redox properties.

Experimental

$[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ (Salen = NN'-disalicylidene ethylenediamine) was prepared by the known method of Lewis *et al*⁹ and purified by recrystallisation from pure chloroform. Molybdenum pentachloride (G. R., E. Merck) preserved in a sealed tube was used. All other chemicals were of pure grade and whenever needed were further purified. The solvents were always distilled before use.

The polarograms were recorded with a Radelkis OH 101/1 polarograph having an automatic current-voltage recording device using a saturated calomel reference electrode through a saturated KCl-agar salt bridge. A Guoy balance was used to measure room temperature magnetic susceptibility. Solution and infrared spectra were recorded with Carl Zeiss PMQ II and Beckman spectrophotometer respectively.

Preparation of the complex: The complex was obtained as an adduct of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ with anhydrous molybdenum pentachloride. To a clear

chloroform solution of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ a clear solution of molybdenum pentachloride was added slowly with stirring, keeping the concentration of the former slightly in excess over the stoichiometric amount. The resulting solution was kept at room temperature to allow the greenish precipitate to settle; the colour of the supernatant solution remained deep red. The precipitate was filtered under suction, repeatedly washed with anhydrous chloroform to remove excess $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ and dried in vacuum.

The compound was decomposed with sodium peroxide. The precipitate was dissolved in hydrochloric acid and estimated for iron volumetrically with dichromate. The filtrate, free from iron, was used for molybdenum analysis as oxinate. Chloride was estimated gravimetrically as silver chloride.

Oxidation state of molybdenum was determined by dissolving about 100 mg of the complex in 0.1 N sulphuric acid and titrating with standard ceric ammonium sulphate using ferroin as indicator, the first distinct change in colour (red to nearly colourless) indicating the end point corresponding to complete oxidation of molybdenum(V) to molybdenum(VI). The result corresponded to an oxidation state of +5 with an error limit of $\pm 3\%$. The analytical data on $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}(\text{MoOCl}_5)_2$ are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL DATA ON $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ AND $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}(\text{MoOCl}_5)_2$

Complex	Percentages of				
	O	N	Cl	Fe	Mo
$[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$	Calcd. : 58.22	8.48	—	16.91	
	Found : 57.84	8.38	—	17.07	
$[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}(\text{MoOCl}_5)_2$	Calcd. : 35.02	5.10	19.39	10.18	17.50
	Found : 34.90	4.95	19.60	10.26	17.30

Results and Discussion

The easy formation of the adduct indicates the formation of an adduct of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ with MoCl_5 itself. Low percentage of chlorine can be rationalised in terms of MoOCl_3 as the adduct forming species. The high affinity of MoCl_5 for oxygen either from atmosphere or from impurities in the solvent becomes a reality even when the preparation was done in anhydrous chloroform. The elemental analysis agrees with the formulation $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}(\text{MoOCl}_3)_2$. Earlier reports¹⁰⁻¹³ show that the two phenolic oxygen atoms in the salen are the only potential coordination sites for further coordination with metal halides. The structure of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ is favourable for coordination with two MoOCl_3 units satisfying the strong affinity of Mo for oxygen at one end and its usual coordination number of six in a somewhat octahedral symmetry. Steric considerations and stability of the complex point to a greater symmetric binding of Mo to two phenolic oxygen atoms of different salen molecules as shown in the proposed structure (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Structure of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}(\text{MoOCl}_3)_2$.

The greenish solid complex gives intense red coloured solution in most solvents. In oxygen containing solvents like ethanol it undergoes slow decomposition. Dimethylformamide being a better solvent with respect to stability and solubility and that is why its spectra was taken in this solvent. The spectra of the adduct appear as broad shoulder in the visible region with about two-fold increase in intensity as compared with $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ (Fig. 2). The enhanced intensity of colour in the adduct may arise from charge-transfer involving the oxidising and reducing metal centres, namely, Fe(III) and Mo(V). The ~ 360 nm band (as shoulder) of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ shifts to lower energy (~ 25 nm) in the adduct. The band around 360 nm in $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ has been shown to have M-O charge-transfer origin peculiar to OXO-bridged complexes¹⁴. Adduct formation somehow dramatically influence this transition.

Magnetic moment of the iron complex has a corrected magnetic moment of 1.80 B.M. at 31°, showing a strong antiferro-magnetic interaction between the metal ion centres^{9,15}. The molybdenum adduct has a value of 6.50 B.M. at 29°. The additive magnetic moment for the iron complex and spin only value of two Mo(V) ions (d^1) computes to 5.26 B.M. which is lower than the experimental value. A plausible explanation can be the reduction

Fig. 2. Spectra of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ ($1-10^{-4}M$; 1'- $0.5 \times 10^{-4}M$) and $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}(\text{MoOCl}_3)_2$ ($2-10^{-4}M$; 2'- $0.5 \times 10^{-4}M$) in dimethylformamide.

of paramagnetic-interaction between two Fe(III) ions following adduct formation with MoOCl_3 , which in effect flattens the Fe-O-Fe angle increasing the Fe-Fe distance following redistribution of the electron density in the Fe-O-Fe region. However, such speculations are to be verified from further temperature dependent magnetic moment and ESR study on the complex which are being undertaken.

While most of the peaks of the parent complex are preserved in the infrared spectra of the adduct with significant shifts in the expected order (Table 2), some additional features are identified (Fig. 3). Thus a new rather broad peak at 360 cm^{-1} can be characterised as Mo-Cl frequency. Fe-O (bridging) frequencies in the complex (792, 825) move to higher energy in the adduct (810, 832 respectively). The new band at 856 cm^{-1} can be assigned to a Mo-O (MoOCl_3) vibration. Significant shift ($\sim 20\text{ cm}^{-1}$) to lower energy is also observed in the region $1600-1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ showing C=N stretching. These results are consistent with the structure of the adduct proposed. A stronger Fe-O (bridging) bond results from a better π -bonding which is formed by a more linear Fe-O-Fe bond, increasing the Fe-O-Fe angle from the expected value 142.2° of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ ¹⁴. The separation between the two iron atoms, which have value of about 3.39 \AA at close approach in the $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ ¹⁵, increases as reflected in the high magnetic moment. MoOCl_3 coordinate to the phenolic oxygen sites has two effects: (i) reduces electron density on O which is compensated by electron redistribution in Fe-N region and the aromatic ring; marked changes in the vibration due to the aromatic ring and the weakening of C=N stretching mode is thus explained, (ii) in order to

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA ON $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ AND $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}(\text{MoOCl}_3)_2$

$[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$	$[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}(\text{MoOCl}_3)_2$
—	360
580	550
600	617
615	
730(sh)	725(sh)
740(sh)	745
750(sh)	
758	
792	810
825	832
	856
905	895(sh)
955	
970	
1028	1008
1050	1015(sh)
1088	1030
1127	1118
1147	1153
1195	
1240	1225
1305	1270
1338	1340
1385	1382
1445	1395(sh)
1465	1435
1525	1550(sh)
1598	1578
1624	1603
	1652

the other hand two oxygen atoms from two different salen moieties would be just suitable for coordination. $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ can be recovered from the adducts unchanged which excludes the other possibility of a binuclear configuration containing one Fe(III) and one Mo(V) centres.

Polarograms of the iron and iron-molybdenum complexes were taken in dimethylformamide containing 0.1M anhydrous LiCl as supporting electrolyte. The two metal reduction waves of the $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ moves to negative potentials in the adduct. The first wave moves from a $E_{1/2}$ value of -0.69 V to -0.98 V and the second wave from -1.28 V to -1.38 V. These data are consistent with the general observation that charge delocalisation takes place toward the Fe(III) centres making these difficultly reducible in the adduct. For the second wave corresponding to reduction of Fe(II) to lower state the effect is expected to be smaller as shown by a shift of 0.1 V.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to the Head of the Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta, for laboratory facilities. Financial assistance of the U. G. C. in the form of a grant to one of the authors (D. K. S.) is also acknowledged.

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Fig. 3. Infrared spectra of $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}$ (.....) and $[\text{Fe}(\text{salen})]_2\text{O}(\text{MoOCl}_3)_2$ (————)

accommodate two bulky group (MoOCl_3) the two salen rings would be further apart. As crowding is not allowed, coordination of MoOCl_3 to the oxygen atom of the same salen is ruled out. On